

Etching of Thin Layers to Atomic Layers: An Overview on Latest Etching Technologies

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Abstract—This paper shows a description of the latest etching technologies developed to satisfy the scaling demand that has been leading the semiconductor industry since its existence, which involves the need to overcome the challenges that come with this scaling such as getting finer feature, avoiding any residues or defects and the latest one being etching at critical atomic scale dimension. Etching, along with lithography, has defined how far a device can be scaled while running under acceptable electrical and mechanical conditions. Improvements of known etching processes to get better profiles on different materials are described along with all the latest technologies. In the latter part of this paper we will take our discussion to etching of very thin layers or atomic layers by a modern technique called atomic layer etching (ALE) and its implementation on oxides and semiconductors. The basic principle of ALE and some characterization tests of ALE will be explored in much detail. The authors will also discuss the advantages of ALE to make positive steps towards sub-10 nm technological node.

Index Terms—Improving planarization: Chemical mechanical polishing, Latest dry etching technologies, FinFET etching, Etching at atomic scale: Atomic layer etching (ALE), Advances in ALE for emerging materials

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a continuous improvement in transistor performance and reduction of feature sizes in the last three decades in semiconductor manufacturing industry. The improvement can be attributed to lithography and etching processes which have been improving every 18 to 24 months and miniaturization of features is going at the pace of Moore's law as a business model for the growth of semiconductor industry. Figure 1 shows the diagram for technology driver presented by ITRS (International Road Map for semiconductors) with addition of topics done by Ishikawa et al. We can say that planar devices were replaced by nonplanar devices to go beyond sub-20 nm technological node which has been termed as "More Moore" direction as per Figure 1. The semiconductor industry moved from wet etching to dry etching in the 1970s and progress in etching has been continuous since then because it is one of the most important unit process which can impact the feature size and performance of the transistor. As said earlier with the advent of nonplanar devices such as FinFET's, vertical transistors etc. etching should be done more efficiently. All the latest etching processes that are currently used in "More Moore" direction will be presented in section II of this paper.

As we are progressing towards nanoelectronics era and size of critical features are getting very small and the need

Fig. 1. Technology drivers and a map of topics reported in [1].

to etch very thin layers is also getting significant. Current Dry etching techniques have certain limitations to etch these so-called atomic layers and process which is used to etch at critical atomic scale dimension is called atomic layer etching (ALE) [1] [2] [3] which is quite analogous to atomic layer deposition. Etching at atomic scale can take technology towards sub-10 nm node which is referred to "Beyond Moore" direction in Figure 1. Many materials have been studied by ALE in the past decade showing remarkable results and will be discussed in section IV of this paper whereas Section III will describe Atomic Layer Etching (ALE), its basic principle and techniques to characterize ALE.

II. IMPROVED ETCHING TECHNOLOGIES

As transistor gets shrunk, different materials are used to solve new challenges in terms of electrical performance and temperature of operation. This brings the need of new fabrication techniques capable of producing the desired dimensions with finer features which are free of defects without compromising speed, life cycle, and power consumption. Precision etching plays a critical role when facing these challenges in the microfabrication processes. Several techniques have been implemented to improve the etching processes of different materials. This section talks about those improvements and latest trends implemented mostly in "more Moore" direction. Advances in several etching processes like improving planarization: Chemical Mechanical Polishing, damascene etching of Copper, Dielectric etching, FinFET etching, Reactive

Ion Etching along with Digital Etching, and new usage of fluorocarbon in atmospheric pressure will be described in this section. Additionally, we show how these methods have been improved to etch sub-20 nm nodes in order to overcome the challenges of getting low defects while achieving finer features. Also, we mention limitations of current dry etching technologies for etching at atomic scale.

A. Improving Planarization: Chemical mechanical polishing

Since CMP is an unavoidable unit process where the degree of polishing is adjusted but also the wafer's surface can suffer a negative impact if the technique is not controlled properly, we also want to talk about its new trends in more details. It's been said that CMP technology was developed after trying several techniques, but also used as a last resort [4]. However, due to the nature of its process, it causes contamination to the wafer because of the polishing abrasives that either adhere to or cut into the surface to be polished. Also, due to the existence of both hard materials (like SiO₂, W, TiN, and TaN) and soft materials (like Al, Cu, and Au) to be removed, the generation of wafer's concavity and convexity is inevitable. For example, when the soft material is polished faster and the hard one, a concave form appears because the latter remains projected. On the other hand, even if the materials have the same hardness, they still have different workability, which always makes the removal rate different. This issue affects the global planarization or uniform planarity across the wafer surface, which is also impacted by the drooping of the wafer edge during the final polishing process, which means that developments are still required to use the abrasives at uniform pressure and motion across the whole wafer. The following two are promising CMP techniques that show a good response to current needs.

1) *Electrolytic CMP (E-CMP)*: Since the upper global routing copper wiring layer, which is located at the top of the wafer surface, is thicker than the other layers under it by ranges between 5-10 times, the CMP process for this top layer requires longer time, leading to a throughput decrease. However, the removal rate can be improved by increasing the CMP pressure, but this will cause the damage to the low-k lower wiring layer. Although there have been techniques to alternate high-speed and high-precision by using two types of slurry, it has been found that switching slurries is not recommendable [4]. Research has led to the implementation of electrolytic processing along with the current CMP (E-CMP), known as a promising alternative that can offer high speeds by keeping low pressures. Also, a non-polluting electro polishing technique has been developed by Ebara Corporation and Osaka University using ultra pure water (ECP-DI) [4].

The damage caused by conventional CMP and the surface micro-roughness can be minimized by applying non-contact electrolytic polishing due to the electrochemical dissolution process, which also prevents the damage to the low-k material during the planarization of the wafer. However, when non-contact technique is used, planarization is not that good, which makes the use of contact E-CMP mandatory.

An example for removing copper, Figure 2 can be used as reference: When the power supply is connected in such a way

Fig. 2. Proposed pattern diagram for E-CMP. Extracted from [4].

Fig. 3. Electrode structure in ECP-DI. Extracted from [4].

that the positive terminal or electrode is in contact with the electrolytic cell pad and the negative terminal with the platen, we get polarization, where the copper wiring film of the wafer acts as the anode and a stainless sheet contained in the cell pad acts as the cathode. This produces an electrochemical reaction that makes the copper wiring films dissolve and be removed. The electrochemical reaction is as follows:

where, Mn^+ represents an electrolyte's positive ion.

2) *Electrolytic Polishing using Ultrapure Water (ECP-DI)*: This alternative takes advantage of the electrochemical interactions between the OH⁻ ions in ultra pure water to polish the atoms in the wafer surface avoiding mechanical damage. Additionally, since ultra pure water is used, the process costs and environmental impact are considerably reduced because extra burden of cleaning after polishing is diminished compared to the use of slurries and electrolyte solutions.

In this unit process a catalyst or ion-exchange material is placed between the wafer and the electrode (shown in Figure 3) in order to make the current density intensify by the acceleration of the ultra pure water molecules' reaction. Then, an external electric field induces the generation of OH⁻ ions to the surface of the wafer to be polished.

In the structure there is a polishing electrode and a power-feeding electrode. The ultra pure water goes between the wafer surface and the ion-exchanger and also between the latter

Fig. 4. Average electric field dependence of the current density. Extracted from [4].

and the electrode. As mentioned, due to the presence of the ion-exchanger, the ultra pure water ion density gets larger increasing the electric current which goes through the power-feeding electrode, the copper surface of the wafer, and then through the polishing electrode as copper gets polished.

To obtain a uniformed polishing of the wafer, attention needs to be put to the electrode and wafer's relative movement, the pressure, the current density, and the area of the polishing electrode. Furthermore, interesting observations over the variation of these parameters show that the removal rate does not change when the relative movement of the wafer and polishing electrode is raised to get better uniformity, but it depends almost linearly on the area of the electrode and current density, which indicates a polishing efficiency almost constant. In addition, it still does polishing at low pressures.

According to experiments made by Ebara Corporation and Osaka University, the use of the catalyst material helps the electrolysis current density take considerably larger values (~1million times) compared to the ones predicted by theory. These results are exposed in Figure 4.

B. Copper Damascene Etching

In order to reduce the delay time RC which increases with higher density package due to reduction of the cross-sectional area of the metal line (getting a larger R) and the reduction in distance between metal lines (getting larger C), the replacement of aluminum and SiO_2 by copper (to reduce resistivity) and a film with a lower dielectric constant (to reduce capacitance) respectively, was introduced. At the same time, a technique called *damascene* had to be implemented to form the Cu metal lines of multilevel interconnection. It consists of alternating SiN and low-k dielectric layers and etching one layer at a time by via-hole etching. The final result of this process is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Copper Damascene etching process. Extracted from [5].

The first SiN layer (called the barrier) is used to prevent the diffusion of the Cu and the low-k layer on top of it hosts the via-holes. The next SiN and low-k layers work as etch stopper and trenches host respectively. The drawback of this technique is that the use of SiN as stopper makes the effective dielectric constant be higher, which affects the real purpose of using a low-k dielectric. In this case, while not using SiN as stopper, then it is necessary to get stability on etch rate for achieving a good trench.

C. Etching of Oxides

Continuous scaling has forced us to look at other materials and silicon dioxide is having limitations such as high leakage current in the "more Moore" direction. We have look at other oxide materials to overcome these limitations and etching is these materials also becomes a vital fabrication process. This section will talk about etching of low-K and high-K oxide materials.

1) *Low-K Etching*: It is a critical unit process that requires special attention to avoid the side effects of the oxygen in the etching gas, which is responsible for degradation of the k-value (higher) and sub trenches formation. This is possible for example, when an oxygen atom from $\text{C}_4\text{F}_8/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ gas interacts with the low-k film molecule such as methylsiloxane based organic spin-on glass (SOG) containing CH_3 , causing the extraction of CH_3 as shown in Figure 6. It has been demonstrated that the sub trenches can be avoided by controlling the concentration of either O_2 or N_2 in the $\text{C}_4\text{F}_8/\text{O}_2/\text{Ar}$ or $\text{C}_4\text{F}_8/\text{N}_2/\text{Ar}$ etcher gases respectively [5]. See Figure 7.

Fig. 6. Subtrench generation during low-k etching. Extracted from [5].

Fig. 7. Etching profile of low-k (methylsiloxane-based organic SOG) by controlling O_2 and C_4F_8 . Extracted from [5].

2) *High-K Etching*: High-k films were introduced as an alternative to prevent the gate current leakage which cannot be ignored at scales of 45 nm nodes and smaller. These dielectrics help to keep the same equivalent oxide thickness (EOT) that is achieved with thicker gates insulating films bigger than 45 nm nodes. Hafnium based films like HfO_x and $HfSiO_x$ have been investigated as good candidates for high-k materials on 45 nm and 32 nm nodes respectively. On the other hand, regarding the gate electrode, as the device gets smaller the effective gate insulating films thickness becomes larger in the used poly-Si because a depletion layer is formed on it, making it a non-desirable material for next generation devices. Therefore, the best option to avoid such a depletion layer is to use metals such as TiN and TaN which have shown to be good responses as materials for the 45 nm and 32 nm respectively [5]. The metal/high-k etching process can be gate-first or gate-last. The gate etching in the gate-first process faces several challenges like profile control, residues, and amount of substrate etched Si (known as recess). The conventional structure of metal/high-k along with the materials used are shown in Figure 8. Hafnium oxides for the high-k dielectric, TiN or TaN for the metal of about 20 nm thickness, and a cap of about 1 nm thickness between them to adjust threshold voltage of the MOS transistor are used.

For the high-k material like $HfSiO_2$, etching with BCl_3/Cl_2 is relatively easy due to the high-vapor-pressure property of Si halides. Furthermore, several selectivity values can be achieved on different temperatures when the BCl_3/Cl_2 ratio is tuned, making it possible to get infinity HfO_2/SiO_2 selectivity at any temperatures between 30-275 °C [5]. Another challenge that can be well addressed is the cap residues, like La for n-type MOS transistors, which have to be removed fast enough after etching for avoiding their adherence because of the non-volatility of their etch byproducts. When the wet cleaning is made appropriately, a vertical profile is obtained free of residues and without etching substrate Si, as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 8. Conventional structure of metal/high-k stack. Figure extracted from [5].

Fig. 9. Vertical profile of metal gate/high-k after appropriate cleaning. Extracted from [5].

Fig. 10. Etch profile of gate metal/high-k in FinFET. Extracted from [5].

D. FinFET Etching

FinFET is a three-dimensional structure developed for 15 nm MOS nodes and smaller. It is built with a Si fin of about 10 nm in the case of 15 nm nodes, orthogonal to the substrate and surrounded by a gate. This eliminates the short channel effect and gets a larger drain current.

Etching of the FinFET's gate is difficult due to the work needed to avoid the film stays at the fin's bottom corner: First, the main highly anisotropic etching of the poly-Si film is stopped before the metal is exposed. This control is made using optical interference. As next step, the sidewall protector is grown by adjusting the gas ratio in order to proceed with the additional high selectivity etching of poly-Si / metal. Third, the poly-Si stringers that remained in the fins are etched by using an isotropic component, followed by a partially etching of the metal and then a high selectivity of metal / high-k is used to completely etch the remained metal. This also leaves the high-

Fig. 11. InGaAs fins (a) cross-section, (b) stand alone. Extracted from [6].

k material partially etched, leaving the task of removing what is remained to wet etching, which is highly selective under SiO_2 . Figure 10 shows that it is possible to get a vertical profile with no residues.

A new practice [6] has achieved the fabrication of the first self-aligned InGaAs FinFET with sub-20 nm fin width (figure 10), getting the highest transconductance among all the III-V FinFETs when normalized to the trench width (W_f) and also obtaining a high channel aspect ratio along with vertical sidewalls and gate lengths (L_g) of 20 nm using a CMOS-compatible fabrication, which includes gate-last process with RIE and no Lift Off process in the front end. Digital etch is used at the end to get the fins thinner and improve the sidewalls. The most aggressively scaled InGaAs FinFET to date was obtained with this work getting a $W_f=7$ nm and $L_g=20$ nm, with an aspect ratio $AR=5.7$.

E. Vertical Side-Wall RIE of InGaAs for 3D III-V MOSFETs

A modern inductively coupled plasma-reactive ion etching (ICP-RIE) followed by digital etching and using $\text{BCl}_3/\text{SiCl}_3/\text{Ar}$ has been demonstrated to produce InGaAs nanowires with diameters of 20 nm and less along with vertical sidewalls and a high aspect ratio (~ 10) [7]. Since InGaAs has been exploited as a material that can provide a high mobility channel, this is a very interesting step in the fabrication of future scaled devices.

For achieving these models, first, in order to avoid contamination of the chamber by hydrocarbon polymer as well as the near surface dopants' hydrogen passivation, chlorine based gases on CH_4/H_2 or HBr chemistries are used. Then, a vertical etching profile is obtained by utilizing directional BCl_3/Ar plasma with SiCl_4 chemistry (low anisotropy) for the first time. Also, digital etch (DE), in which both the etcher and the energetic beam hit the surface in an alternating way, is used to clean near-surface material that is damaged by RIE. This method can be controlled easily and is made by limiting the O_2 plasma oxidation at low power first and then removing the oxide with diluted H_2SO_4 . This has demonstrated that it has been possible to produce high aspect ratio in 3D devices like vertical InGaAs MOSFETs by using RIE+DE. As an example, Figure 12 exposes two cases with high aspect ratios and in which a smaller diameter but maintaining the shape is obtained after 5 cycles of digital etching.

Fig. 12. (a) InGaAs fabricated with RIE. (b) Same as (a) but after using five DE cycles. Extracted from [7].

F. Limitations of Current Dry Etching Technology and Atomic Layer Etching as an Alternative for etching at Atomic Scale

Dry etching has been dominant etching technique due to fast etch rates and advantages over wet etching. But process variability has been an issue and becomes a bigger issue when etching is done at atomic scale. For example, process variability comes from chamber mismatch, non uniformity across the wafer etc. On the other hand etching of silicon still has to deal with two requirements that may look as contradictory: From one side, the etching of profound holes will require high removal rates, but on the other hand, the very thin gates and the control of substrate's silicon removal must be done by using low etching rates. This is because substrate removal affects the drain current of the transistor and shifts its threshold voltage [5]. To reduce the amount of removed silicon from the substrate, it will be necessary to apply techniques at atomic level, such as ALE (or Atomic Layer Etching), which gives the alternative to etch one atomic layer at a time. This technique will be discussed in the next sections.

III. ETCHING AT ATOMIC SCALE: ATOMIC LAYER ETCHING (ALE)

As discussed in the last section, process variability is one of the biggest disadvantages of etching at atomic scale. All the reactions occurring at the same time in techniques like RIE doesn't provide control for etching at atomic scale. A technique that has been around for the last three decades called atomic layer etching is a good way to control process variability. A basic ALE mechanism splits the reactions into two parts called modification and removal in its simplest way of implementation. However, some ALE methods have more than two mechanisms but the paper will not discuss them for the simplicity of the explanation. Along with the discussion of ALE basic principle, the section will also discuss some characterization tests for ALE which are required to design the process for a specific reactant and substrate combination.

A. ALE Principle

The basic principle of etching at atomic scale is splitting the reaction into steps [1] [2] [3]. As discussed above, splitting into two reactions is the simplest way of implementation as shown in Figure 13. It is worth to mention here that these reactions are self-limiting which means the reaction should slow down or completely stop with respect to time. In atomic layer etching, layers are etched per cycle which is resembling

Fig. 13. Generalized structure and analogy between ALD and ALE is shown. Extracted from [1].

to growth per cycle in Atomic layer deposition. First reaction in ALE is called modification mechanism and second one is known as removal mechanism. Each step should be done independently of the other and purging should be done after the modification step so that no excess reactant should remain in the chamber. Modification mechanism can be done in various ways such as chemisorption, deposition, conversion, extraction etc. and can be done using plasma, neutral gases, low emission of UV light etc. Removal mechanism can be done using ion bombardment, thermal energy, chemical removal etc. and the removal methods defines if the etching is directional because most of the process in semiconductor industry needs directional etching. Directional ALE can be achieved if ion bombardment is used to remove the modified layer [3]. Table I compares the basic characteristics of thermal ALE, plasma ALE and conventional plasma etching techniques. Although we must say that the anisotropic ALE using plasma enhanced approach is popular in semiconductor process industry because radicals produced by plasma are reactive in modification step and plasma is important for removal step because it provides anisotropic (directional) etching.

B. Characterization Tests for Atomic Layer Etching

The need to characterize is to check whether the ALE process is near ideal or not. Various test to characterize ALE has been studied, but we will limit our discussion to only three tests that have been reported the most. The first one being synergy test which means relative amount of material that is etched per cycle [8]. It checks whether favorable etching is done by the modification and removal step. Synergy can be formulated as total percentage of relative material that is etched per cycle. The formula for synergy percentage is:

$$ALE \text{ synergy } \% = \frac{EPC - (\alpha + \beta)}{EPC} \times 100 \%$$

Where EPC is etch per cycle and $(\alpha + \beta)$ is undesirable values from each reaction. Synergy test is popular because it is simple and can be used to compare different ALE mechanisms. Ideal synergy for etch cycle for ALE is 100 % which is obvious from the equation above. Kanim et al. formulated synergy in terms of energies of underlying surface interactions and performed synergy analysis on various materials.

Fig. 14. Saturation curves showing self-limiting removal in (a) ALE for small EPC, (b) ALE for larger EPC, and (c) ALE quasi-self-limiting. In curve (d) current dry etching techniques lacking self limiting behaviour. Extracted from [2].

Fig. 15. Illustration of an energy scan for the ALE removal step. Region II demonstrates ALE window. Extracted from [2].

As discussed earlier ALE consists of self-limiting reactions and one way to characterize it is by looking at saturation curve [2]. Figure 14 shows the reaction has to saturate with respect to time. Different materials can be studied using this method and self-limiting behavior can be understood. Figure 14 also shows the quasi self-limiting regime where self-limiting behavior can be seen but with minor trade off. The next way to characterize ALE is by doing an energy scan which means energy in removal step due to ion, thermal etc. should be in ALE energy window as shown in Figure 15.

TABLE I
BASIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THERMAL ALE, PLASMA ALE AND PLASMA ETCHING PROCESS

	Thermal ALE	Plasma ALE	Plasma Etching
Method	It is a discontinuous process having two thermal self-limiting reactions of modification and removal. The conformal removal of atomic layer is achieved by these reactions.	It is also a discontinuous process having two self-limiting reactions of modification and removal. Surface removal is done by plasma bombardment. Modification may be heat or plasma assisted.	It is a continuous process containing a reactive gas. Plasma generates chemically active species and interaction of these species on the surface forms volatile products. It is physical and chemical etching.
Advantage	Self-limiting, conformal etching, smooth etched surface, ALE window, selective etching, isotropic etching, atomic layer precision	Self-limiting, ALE window, directional etching, selective etching, Low process temperature, atomic layer precision	High etching rate, low process temperature, high throughput, directional etching, selective etching
Disadvantage	Low etching rate, directional etching not possible, throughput, process temperature	Low etching rate, wafer scale uniformity, complex plasma physics and chemistry	Plasma damage, chemical residue, etching at atomic scale not possible, etching accuracy

As the modified layer requires less energy to be removed as compared to unmodified layer thus leading to the existence of the ALE energy window. Region II in the Figure 15 shows ALE energy window in which complete removal is done. While region I show incomplete removal and Region III shows over etching. In general, all these ALE characterization techniques are important to understand ALE process in terms to time and energy.

IV. MATERIALS ETCHED BY ALE: A CASE STUDY

We can naively say that ALE is opposite process of atomic layer deposition. The total number of materials studied with ALE are still less as compared to materials studied by ALD, so there is a good research opportunity to study other material. We will discuss materials like oxides, metals and compound semiconductor. From a long time, researchers are experimentally looking at a variety of self-limiting reactions and these mechanisms are looked carefully in this section. As discussed in the previous sections a basic ALE mechanisms has a modification step and a removal step. Modification mechanisms include chemisorption, deposition, extraction, conversion etc. whereas removal step consists of process like thermal desorption, particle bombardment, chemical reaction etc.

A. Oxides

1) *Silicon dioxide (SiO₂)*: The oxide which has been used widely in CMOS technology for a long period of time is silicon dioxide which has been a backbone for silicon CMOS technology. The major breakthrough with respect to atomic layer etching of silicon dioxide came in last decade when a fluorocarbon deposition based ALE approach was developed [9] and various simulations came before appropriate experimental data. Metzler et al. experimentally used this fluorocarbon deposition based ALE approach to etch the most used oxide in semiconductor industry. For further clarification, deposition base ALE is having alternate deposition and etching steps which is quite similar to Bosch process (used to protect the feature sidewall). As discussed above molecular dynamic simulations came before [10] experimental results. Metzler et al. used the same ideas which were shown in molecular dynamic simulations by Rauf et al. to examine the possibility of ALE mechanism using fluorocarbon in the modification step

Fig. 16. Example of Thickness evolution during eight cycles of silicon dioxide ALE process. Extracted from [9].

which is followed by Argon ion etching. It's worth mentioning here that fluorocarbon layer in the modification step is of nanometer-scale.

Angstrom thick Fluorocarbon layer is deposited to form a modified silicon dioxide as mentioned earlier. In the next step low energy argon ion bombardment is used to remove both the fluorocarbon layer and the reacted silicon dioxide layer which is relatively thin. Etching stops once the thin reacted layer is removed which makes this reaction self-limiting. To deposit fluorocarbon layer, pulsed C_4F_8 is introduced into a low power Argon plasma. Figure 16 clears the picture in a better way [9] in which thickness evolution and etching in multiple cycles are shown along with process parameter. Pulsed C_4F_8 is introduced to the oxide layer for 1.5 seconds and then after waiting for 8 seconds RF bias potential is applied which activates the argon ion bombardment as shown in Figure 16. Hudson et al. showed that the mechanism discussed above is selective to silicon nitride. This is a very important breakthrough because silicon nitride is used as gate spacers in some applications and silicon dioxide can be etched without removing the nitride layer.

2) *Hafnium oxide (HfO₂)*: With continuous scaling of the CMOS technology, silicon dioxide is having big concerns with the leakage and reliability of the transistor. Various alternatives have been explored over the past few years [2] and among them hafnium oxide has the potential due to its material properties like wide band gap, high dielectric constant, low

Fig. 17. Change in etch rate as function of gas pressure and RMS roughness with the comparison between Cl_2 & BCl_3 reactant gas. Extracted from [11].

leakage current and good thermal stability. Various other high-dielectric oxides such as titanium dioxide, aluminum oxide and beryllium oxide has also been studied in the past decade [2] with the interest of etching at atomic scale. But we will limit ourselves to hafnium oxide for discussion of ALE.

Atomic scale etching of silicon in which chlorine is introduced at the modification step but in case of hafnium oxide, chlorine is insufficient to form a reactive layer with oxygen. To overcome this Boron tetrachloride gas (BCl_3) is employed because the bond between boron and oxygen is strong enough to form the reactive layer with oxygen. In a typical cycle as described by park et al. in which BCl_3 is supplied for 20 seconds to etch chamber so that Hafnium oxide absorb the reactant gas. The neutral beam such as Argon is turned on for 10 seconds to remove absorbed species in the subsequent step. Taking the discussion further, as mentioned above BCl_3 is used as reactant gas for the reason of having higher binding energy between boron and oxygen bond and during the argon beam bombardment oxygen from HfO_2 is removed as boron oxychlorides. Figure 17 shows the change etch rate as function of gas pressure and RMS roughness with the comparison between Cl_2 & BCl_3 gas used as reactant. Another interesting study reveals that among the various methods for etching HfO_2 , the surface concentration of hafnium and oxide remains relatively constant after ALE as compare to mechanisms like ICP. In case of ICP atomic percentage of hafnium and oxide change rapidly making it hafnium rich as shown in Figure 18. Some studies also reveal that etch damage can be reduced by ALE [11].

3) *Silicon nitride* (Si_3N_4): Silicon nitride has large dielectric constant as compared silicon oxide and was once thought as a replacement of SiO_2 but could deliver due to the tunneling effect observed in nitrides. However, it is still important in certain device applications where used as a gate spacer, passivation dielectric etc. It's worth mentioning here that the generic process discussed in the article which is introduction of chlorine in the modification step is not adequate in case of silicon nitride because bond between silicon and nitrogen have high binding energy. Posseme et al. introduced a new approach for etching of silicon nitride in comparison to the generic

Fig. 18. Hafnium to oxygen ratio with different etching methods. Extracted from [11].

Fig. 19. Description of nitrite spacer etching using an alternate approach. Extracted from [12].

approach [13] in which the modification is done in form of extraction in which silicon nitride exposed to hydrogen to form ammonia and a subsequent ion bombardment is introduced in the removal step.

The new approach which Posseme et al. named “thin layer etching” consists of two steps [12]. Light ion implantation performed in plasma is done as a first step to modify the silicon nitride layer and modification has been done in the form of conversion. In the subsequent removal step wet etching is performed typically with HF solution to remove the modified layer and the non-modified layer remains as a spacer shown in figure 4.

B. Semiconductor

1) *Silicon*: Silicon has been a dominant semiconductor material in industry. Atomic layer etching can be achieved by chlorination in the modification step and argon ion bombardment in the removal step. Chlorination can be done thermally or using plasma as discussed in Table I. Using Plasma for chlorination increases the etching rate. The main purpose of the modification step is to easily remove the unmodified layer and chlorination does the same phenomena with modification of Si-Si bonds. The binding energy of Si-Si bond which is 3.4 eV is reduced to 2.3 (Si-Cl bond). Argon ion bombardment

TABLE II
SUMMARY OF REPORTED ATOMIC LAYER ETCHING OF MATERIALS WITH THEIR CORRESPONDING MODIFICATION CHEMISTRIES AND ETCHING ENERGY SOURCES.

Materials	Modification Mechanism	Modification method	Removal Mechanism	Ion energy (eV)	Selectivity	Etching rate (Å/cycle)	Directional etching	Synergy	Reference
Silicon	Cl_2 plasma	Chemisorption	Argon ion	20-50	to silicon dioxide	15	Yes	90 %	[2] [8] [1]
Silicon dioxide	CHF_3 plasma	-	Argon ion	30-50	-	1-4	Yes	80 %	[2] [1] [8]
Silicon nitride	C_4F_8 gas	deposition	Argon ion	<30	to Si	4	-	-	[9] [2] [1]
	He plasma	conversion	Wet etching	-	-	20-60	-	-	[12] [2] [1]
	CHF_3 plasma	extraction	Argon ion	20-25	to silicon dioxide	4-12	-	-	[13] [2] [1]
Hafnium oxide	BCl_3 gas	chemisorption	Neutral argon beam	-	-	-	No	-	[11] [2] [1]
GaAs	Cl_2 gas	chemisorption	Argon ion	15-25	-	10-15	-	-	[14] [2] [1]
GaN	Cl_2 plasma	-	Argon ion	60-80	-	-	Yes	91 %	[2] [1]

is done in the ALE window to remove the modified layer in the removal step as discussed in Table II. This technique was illustrated by Lam research corporation [15] and they found infinite selectivity of silicon to bulk thermally grown silicon dioxide. The concept of using halogen gases like chlorine and fluorine is a fundamental in plasma etching but the main difference in ALE is modification and removal are separate steps.

However, we must say that this process is not always perfect. ALE of silicon will be ideal when chlorination forms a well-defined modified layer and argon ion just remove this layer. But there can be non-ideal reactions such as etching during chlorination and sputtering during removal step. However chemical etching is not a big concern during thermal chlorination but plasma chlorination increases the probability of it. This challenge can be addressed by operating in a plasma process regime that minimize generation of radicals. Sputtering during removal step can also be a problem is ion energy is not delivered within the ALE window. There have been several proposals to replace Argon with other atoms to lower sputtering.

2) *Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)*: For a long time gallium arsenide (GaAs) was thought of an alternative to silicon in CMOS technology. Considering an end of road for silicon due to its material properties, researchers started looking into other semiconductor materials to replace silicon and GaAs was considered as good choice for replacements though having some issues with the hole mobility for PMOS in the complementary pair. So it's very fair to take our discussion of atomic scale etching towards GaAs.

From all the studies done on ALE of GaAs [14], a bulk of them discussed chemisorption using chlorine in the modification step and argon ion bombardment in the removal step. Aoyagi et al. reported first time molecular layer etching of GaAs which is self-limiting [14]. The experiments performed by them were alternating introduction of etchant of chlorine and applying Argon ion beam for removal step. Figure 20 shows etching rate as a function of chlorine feeding gas. The etching rate decreases after 20 seconds of feeding time because chlorine atom is absorbed in the GaAs and thickness of absorbed layer increase rapidly.

Fig. 20. Etching rate as function of Cl_2 feeding time. Extracted from [14].

V. CONCLUSION

We have looked at new techniques for planarization of wafer surface and etching of nonplanar devices such as FinFET for making progress towards 20 nm technological node. Improved etching technologies in "more Moore" direction does not look promising technique for etching at atomic scale due to limitations such as process variability. ALE looks well aligned to help in fabrication of devices below the 10 nm technological node. Semiconductor industry has looked into new techniques like plasma assisted ALE to make ALE faster and cheaper. However, certain applications may permit slower ALE because of increasing opportunity of atomic layer removal. We have discussed ALE basic principle and some materials that can be etched by ALE. However, there are challenges like control on atomic layer reactions, surface quality etc. These challenges can be a good outline for research on atomic layer fidelity of dry technology. We purpose that these challenges should be addressed with experimental approach to make progress towards "Beyond Moore" direction. Eventually, ALE may not

be needed in every application because each application will have its own requirements and trade-offs.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. Ishikawa, K. Karahashi, T. Ichiki, J. P. Chang, S. M. George, W. M. M. Kessels, H. J. Lee, S. Tinck, J. H. Um, and K. Kinoshita, "Progress and prospects in nanoscale dry processes: How can we control atomic layer reactions?" *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 56, no. 6S2, pp. 06HA02–1–06HA02–13, 2017. [Online]. Available: 10.7567/JJAP.56.06HA02
- [2] K. J. Kanarik, T. Lill, E. A. Hudson, S. Sriraman, S. Tan, J. Marks, V. Vahedi, and R. A. Gottscho, "Overview of atomic layer etching in the semiconductor industry," *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology*, vol. 33, no. 020802, pp. 020802–1–020802–14, 2015. [Online]. Available: 10.1116/1.4913379
- [3] T. Lill, K. J. Kanarik, S. Tan, S. Berry, A. Fischer, V. Vahedi, and R. A. Gottscho, "Atomic Layer Etching: Benefits and Challenges," in *IEEE Electron Devices Technology and Manufacturing Conference (EDTM), 13-16 March 2018, Kobe, Japan*, vol. 2, 2018 IEEE 2nd Electron Devices Technology and Manufacturing Conference (EDTM), March 2018, pp. 41–43. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8421486>
- [4] T. Doi, I. D. Marinescu, and S. Kurokawa, *Advances in CMP Polishing Technologies*, 1st ed. Elsevier Inc., December 2011.
- [5] K. Nojiri, *Dry Etching Technology for Semiconductors*, 1st ed. Springer International Publishing, 2015.
- [6] A. Vardi, J. Lin, W. Lu, X. Zhao, and J. A. del Alamo, "High aspect ratio InGaAs FinFETs with sub-20 nm fin width," in *2016 IEEE Symposium on VLSI Technology, 14-16 June, Honolulu, HI, USA*, June 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7573408>
- [7] X. Zhao and J. A. del Alamo, "Nanometer-Scale Vertical-Sidewall Reactive Ion Etching of InGaAs for 3-D III-V MOSFETs," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 521–523, May 2014. [Online]. Available: 10.1109/LED.2014.2313332
- [8] K. J. Kanarik, S. Tan, W. Yang, T. Kim, T. Lill, A. Kabansky, E. A. Hudson, T. Ohba, K. Nojiri, J. Yu, R. Wise, I. L. Berry, Y. Pan, J. Marks, and R. A. Gottscho, "Predicting synergy in atomic layer etching," *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 05C302–1–05C302–7, 2017. [Online]. Available: 10.1116/1.4979019
- [9] D. Metzler, R. L. Bruce, S. Engelmann, E. A. Joseph, and G. S. Oehrlein, "Fluorocarbon assisted atomic layer etching of SiO₂ using cyclic Ar/C₄F₈ plasma," *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 020603–1–020603–4, 2014. [Online]. Available: 10.1116/1.4843575
- [10] S. Rauf, T. Sparks, P. L. G. Ventzek, V. V. Smirnov, A. V. Stengach, K. G. Gaynullin, and V. A. Pavlovsky, "A molecular dynamics investigation of fluorocarbon based layer-by-layer etching of silicon and SiO₂," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 101, no. 3, pp. 033308–1–033308–9, 2007. [Online]. Available: 10.1063/1.2464192
- [11] S. D. Park, W. S. Lim, B. J. Park, H. C. Lee, J. W. Bae, and G. Y. Yeoma, "Precise Depth Control and Low-Damage Atomic-Layer Etching of HfO₂ using BCl₃ and Ar Neutral Beam," *Electrochemical and Solid-State Letters*, vol. 11, pp. H71–H73, 2008.
- [12] N. Posseme, O. Pollet, and S. Barnola, "Alternative process for thin layer etching: Application to nitride spacer etching stopping on silicon germanium," *Journal of Applied physics*, vol. 105, pp. 051605–1–051605–4, 2014. [Online]. Available: 10.1063/1.4892543
- [13] T. Matsuura, Y. Honda, and J. Murota, "Atomic-order layer-by-layer role-share etching of silicon nitride using an electron cyclotron resonance plasma," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 74, pp. 3573–3575, 1999. [Online]. Available: 10.1063/1.124165
- [14] Y. Aoyagi, K. Shinmura, K. Kawasaki, T. Tanaka, K. Gamo, S. Namba, and I. Nakamoto, "Molecular layer etching of GaAs," *Journal of Applied physics*, vol. 60, pp. 968–970, 1992. [Online]. Available: 10.1063/1.106477
- [15] S. Tan, W. Yang, K. J. Kanarik, T. Lill, V. Vahedi, J. Marks, and R. A. Gottscho, "Highly Selective Directional Atomic Layer Etching of Silicon," *Solid State Science and technology*, vol. 54, no. 14, pp. N5010–N5012, 2014.

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